

Supplementary Information

This document contains the *Supplementary Information* for Stoeckel et al., 2024 published in *Peer Community Journal*, linked to the data deposited on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10246264>, Stoeckel et al., 2023).

Preprint version 4 of this article has been peer-reviewed and recommended by *Peer Community In Evolutionary Biology* (<https://doi.org/10.24072/pci.evolbiol.100788>, Alvarez, 2024).

References

- Alvarez I (2024) Mixed reproduction modes explain a high genetic diversity in the invasive plant *Ludwigia grandiflora* subsp. *hexapetala* in western Europe. *Peer Community in Evolutionary Biology*, **1**, 100788. <https://doi.org/10.24072/pci.evolbiol.100788>
- Stoeckel S, Barloy D, Portillo Lemus L, Becheler R (2023) Genotyping measures and population genetic indices for assessing reproductive modes of polyploid *Ludwigia grandiflora* subsp. *hexapetala* in western Europe. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10246264>
- Stoeckel S, Becheler R, Portillo-Lemus L, Harang M, Besnard A-L, Lassalle G, Causse-Védrines R, Michon-Coudouel S, Park DJ, Pope BJ, Petit EJ, Barloy D (2024) Reproductive modes in populations of late-acting self-incompatible and self-compatible polyploid *Ludwigia grandiflora* subsp. *hexapetala* in western Europe. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.03.21.586104>

Situation of *Lgh* in USA and Mediterranean populations in previous studies (Dandelot 2004, Okada et al., 2009, Armitage et al., 2013):

- nearly monoclonal populations arguing for the ecological advantage of clonality (fragmentation and rhizome propagation) in these invasive populations.

But

- using weakly polymorphic markers,
- before the demonstration of the heterostyly and of the Late-acting self-incompatibility system in *Lgh*

Situation of *Lgh* in western Europe, studied here:

- Spatial context: The other compatible type populations are away from hundreds of meters to several kilometers (Portillo-Lemus et al., 2021)

- Clonality through fragmentation and rhizomes, as in other populations (Portillo-Lemus 2021).

- Massive blossoming with a lot of pollinators harvesting flowers (Portillo-Lemus 2021).

- Faster pollen tube elongation of pollen from the other compatible type (Portillo-Lemus et al., 2022)

Our working hypotheses about the main, realized reproductive modes in population:

- **LSI populations:** A very limited production of seeds (Portillo-Lemus et al., 2021)

Hypothesis 1: preferential clonality due to lack of compatible partners to produce seeds → Baker's conjecture on reproductive modes (Pannell et al., 2015).

Hypothesis 2: The rare seeds really contribute to the populations → biological feature of seeds or recombination would have advantage over clones. If so, are they mainly:

Selfed seeds → reproductive assurance and advantage of recombination over clonality in a uniparental context?

Outcrossed seeds → advantage of outcrossed seeds due to heterosis and/or recombination despite the lack of locally-available compatible partners → selection of long pollination ranges

- **SC populations:** Production of a lot of seeds in natural populations

Hypothesis 1: despite a huge production of seeds, preferential clonality due to the physiological and/or ecological advantage of clones over seed germination process?

Hypothesis 2: the mass of seeds does contribute to the populations or some evolutionary advantage of recombination in offspring compared to clonal fragmentation and rhizome propagation to adapt local conditions? If so, are these seeds mainly:

Selfed seeds → within uniparental reproduction, biological feature of seeds or genetic recombination would provide advantage over clones?

Outcrossed seeds → Faster pollen tube elongation of pollen from the other type gives real advantage or advantage to allogamy to adapt new local conditions?

Supplementary information1: Synthesis of the questionings of our study to estimate reproductive modes of 53 populations of invasive *Lgh* using genetic diversity on the autotetraploid part of its genome.

Stoeckel S, Becheler R, Portillo-Lemus L, Harang M, Besnard A-L, Lassalle G, Causse-Védrines R, Michon-Coudouel S, Park DJ, Pope BJ, Petit EJ, Barloy D (2024) Reproductive modes in populations of late-acting self-incompatible and self-compatible polyploid *Ludwigia grandiflora* subsp. *hexapetala* in western Europe. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.03.21.586104>

Genotypic or genetic index	Range of values	Main driver	Behavior	references
β^*	$\in [0; +\infty]$	Rate of clonality	\downarrow when c \uparrow $\beta \rightarrow 0$ when c $\rightarrow 1$	Halkett et al., 2005, Arnaud-Haond et al., 2007, 2020, Stoeckel et al., 2021
$\text{var}F_{IS}$	$\in [0; +\infty]$	Rate of clonality	\uparrow when c \uparrow $\text{Var}F_{IS} \rightarrow 0$ when c $\rightarrow 0$	Stoeckel & Masson 2014, Stoeckel et al., 2021
r_d	$\in [0; 1]$	Rate of selfing	slightly \uparrow when c \uparrow \uparrow when s \uparrow $r_d \rightarrow 1$ when s $\rightarrow 1$	Weir and Cockerham 1973, Navascues et al., 2010, Halkett et al., 2005
H_o	$\in [0; 1]$	Rate of selfing	\downarrow when s \uparrow $H_o \rightarrow 0$ when s $\rightarrow 1$	David et al., 2007, Halkett et al., 2005
F_{IS}	$\in [-1; 1]$	Both rates	\downarrow when c \uparrow $F_{IS} \rightarrow -1$ when c $\rightarrow 1$ $F_{IS} \rightarrow +1$ when s $\rightarrow 1$	Stoeckel & Masson 2014, Balloux et al., 2003, Stoeckel et al., 2021
H_E	$\in [0; 1]$	Rate of selfing	\downarrow when s \uparrow $H_E \rightarrow 0$ when s $\rightarrow 1$	Glémin et al., 2001, Ritland & Ganders 1987
P_{ID-SIB}	$\in [0; +\infty]$	Both rates	\downarrow when c \uparrow \downarrow when s \uparrow	Waits et al., 2001
S_g^{**}	$\in [0; 1]$	Rate of selfing	\uparrow when s \uparrow	David et al., 2007, Hardy et al., 2016

* similar behavior of the clonal richness R

** inferred values of s, according to the method of Hardy (2016)

Table SI1: Hypotheses about the influence of clonality and selfing on the expected variations of genetic indices.

Stoeckel S, Becheler R, Portillo-Lemus L, Harang M, Besnard A-L, Lassalle G, Causse-Védrines R, Michon-Coudouel S, Park DJ, Pope BJ, Petit EJ, Barloy D (2024) Reproductive modes in populations of late-acting self-incompatible and self-compatible polyploid *Ludwigia grandiflora* subsp. *hexapetala* in western Europe. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.03.21.586104>

			Measured population genetic indices														Relative rankings of reproduction modes													
Population	Mating	Morph	G	R	D*	Pareto's β	HO	var(ho)	HE	var(he)	AE	var(Ae)	FIS	var(FIS)	rd	PIDu	PIDsb	Sg	SE(Sg)	rk_cl	sn_cl	rk_self	sn_self	z_β (i)	z_varFis (i)	z_rD (i)	z_MFis (i)	z_Sg (i)	Σclon	Σself
AiC	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.31	1.84	0.25	1.14	1.40	3.90	-0.241	15.60	0.128	5.70E-09	1.01E-04	0.00	0.00	8	0.199	26	0.157	0.000	0.398	0.331	0.436	0.000	0.199	0.256
AiL	LSI	L	11	0.71	3.17	0.68	0.27	2.40	0.21	1.37	1.34	4.19	-0.308	25.88	0.103	1.29E-07	4.51E-04	0.04	0.05	42	0.740	18	0.125	0.787	0.692	0.287	0.108	0.069	0.740	0.155
AiP	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.38	1.01	0.33	0.56	1.55	2.73	-0.147	2.84	0.233	8.47E-12	4.16E-06	0.10	0.20	2	0.016	45	0.311	0.000	0.031	0.515	0.897	0.172	0.016	0.528
ApE	LSI	L	12	0.79	3.40	1.48	0.26	2.56	0.20	1.52	1.35	4.88	-0.295	28.64	0.120	1.48E-07	4.84E-04	0.00	0.01	30	0.644	16	0.124	0.517	0.772	0.317	0.172	0.000	0.644	0.163
ApP	LSI	L	12	0.79	3.40	1.48	0.26	2.59	0.21	1.53	1.35	5.06	-0.273	29.24	0.175	1.62E-07	5.20E-04	0.08	0.08	32	0.653	34	0.199	0.517	0.789	0.413	0.279	0.124	0.653	0.272
Av	LSI	L	13	0.86	3.52	1.91	0.30	1.95	0.24	1.10	1.39	3.93	-0.235	7.37	0.279	6.65E-09	1.18E-04	0.42	0.26	14	0.266	49	0.424	0.371	0.161	0.595	0.466	0.694	0.266	0.585
Bl	LSI	L	13	0.86	3.52	1.91	0.21	1.66	0.18	1.08	1.28	3.37	-0.177	20.00	0.263	1.33E-06	1.50E-03	0.52	0.20	27	0.447	51	0.486	0.371	0.524	0.567	0.750	0.853	0.447	0.723
Bo	LSI	L	10	0.64	3.15	0.95	0.27	2.51	0.20	1.46	1.34	4.50	-0.308	27.57	0.088	1.67E-07	4.96E-04	0.00	0.00	38	0.718	9	0.099	0.695	0.741	0.261	0.108	0.000	0.718	0.123
Ca	LSI	L	12	0.79	3.43	1.32	0.26	2.46	0.20	1.48	1.34	4.77	-0.29	30.00	0.168	1.94E-07	5.83E-04	0.17	0.10	37	0.690	38	0.228	0.570	0.811	0.401	0.196	0.288	0.690	0.295
Ch	LSI	L	12	0.79	3.43	1.32	0.25	2.38	0.20	1.43	1.34	4.42	-0.243	27.91	0.133	3.20E-07	6.87E-04	0.14	0.11	33	0.660	37	0.217	0.570	0.751	0.340	0.426	0.231	0.660	0.333
Cn	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.37	1.59	0.29	0.93	1.47	3.32	-0.267	9.85	0.144	2.13E-10	2.06E-05	0.05	0.10	7	0.116	30	0.174	0.000	0.232	0.359	0.309	0.086	0.116	0.251
Co	LSI	L	3	0.14	1.49	0.06	0.26	2.57	0.20	1.45	1.33	4.42	-0.33	31.86	-0.057	2.43E-07	6.02E-04	0.00	0.00	55	0.932	2	0.002	1.000	0.864	0.007	0.000	0.000	0.932	0.002
Cp	LSI	L	10	0.64	3.21	1.39	0.27	2.46	0.20	1.42	1.34	4.33	-0.309	27.60	0.036	1.69E-07	5.08E-04	0.02	0.03	31	0.645	8	0.077	0.548	0.742	0.170	0.103	0.035	0.645	0.103
Di	LSI	L	11	0.71	3.25	0.95	0.26	2.40	0.20	1.44	1.33	4.43	-0.286	28.25	0.206	2.48E-07	6.05E-04	0.07	0.08	41	0.728	36	0.208	0.695	0.760	0.468	0.216	0.114	0.728	0.266
Eb	LSI	L	15	0.93	3.62	2.91	0.24	2.40	0.20	1.52	1.34	5.31	-0.24	24.88	0.106	2.98E-07	6.49E-04	0.00	0.06	21	0.348	23	0.145	0.032	0.664	0.292	0.441	0.000	0.348	0.245
Gi	LSI	L	14	0.93	3.62	2.91	0.26	2.56	0.20	1.50	1.34	4.63	-0.307	30.77	-0.010	2.21E-07	5.59E-04	0.00	0.00	25	0.432	5	0.042	0.032	0.833	0.089	0.113	0.000	0.432	0.067
Gl	LSI	L	11	0.71	3.30	1.43	0.26	2.50	0.20	1.47	1.34	4.50	-0.304	30.63	0.079	2.26E-07	5.75E-04	0.06	0.06	36	0.682	15	0.12	0.535	0.829	0.245	0.127	0.098	0.682	0.157
Is	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.36	1.53	0.28	0.89	1.46	3.18	-0.26	8.22	0.119	3.01E-10	2.51E-05	0.07	0.13	6	0.093	29	0.169	0.000	0.186	0.315	0.343	0.107	0.093	0.255
La	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.16	1.99	0.13	1.19	1.22	3.95	-0.261	29.07	0.090	5.22E-05	8.31E-03	0.06	0.21	24	0.392	24	0.15	0.000	0.784	0.264	0.338	0.102	0.392	0.235
Me	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.37	1.18	0.31	0.75	1.51	3.26	-0.197	1.75	0.140	5.14E-11	9.83E-06	0.24	0.18	1	0.000	42	0.289	0.000	0.000	0.352	0.652	0.402	0.000	0.469
Mo	LSI	L	4	0.21	1.72	0.09	0.26	2.56	0.20	1.45	1.33	4.42	-0.329	31.79	-0.061	2.43E-07	6.02E-04	0.00	0.00	54	0.925	1	0.001	0.988	0.862	0.000	0.005	0.000	0.925	0.002
Ne	LSI	L	5	0.29	2.20	0.23	0.26	2.53	0.20	1.46	1.34	4.43	-0.318	31.31	0.051	2.40E-07	5.97E-04	0.02	0.03	53	0.894	33	0.198	0.940	0.848	0.546	0.059	0.036	0.894	0.214
Nv	LSI	L	9	0.57	2.99	0.68	0.26	2.51	0.20	1.46	1.34	4.41	-0.313	31.05	0.252	2.38E-07	5.95E-04	0.00	0.00	46	0.814	7	0.075	0.788	0.841	0.198	0.083	0.000	0.814	0.094
Ol	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.30	2.26	0.23	1.33	1.38	4.13	-0.292	21.90	0.050	2.37E-08	2.00E-04	0.04	0.06	15	0.289	10	0.1	0.000	0.578	0.194	0.186	0.060	0.289	0.147
Or	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.19	1.86	0.16	1.32	1.28	4.84	-0.177	23.79	0.059	3.62E-06	2.30E-03	0.11	0.18	18	0.316	32	0.195	0.000	0.633	0.210	0.750	0.175	0.316	0.378
Pl	LSI	L	14	0.93	3.62	2.91	0.26	2.43	0.20	1.43	1.34	4.46	-0.272	27.60	0.115	2.29E-07	6.19E-04	0.06	0.06	23	0.387	27	0.158	0.032	0.742	0.308	0.284	0.098	0.387	0.230
Po	LSI	L	14	0.93	3.62	2.91	0.32	2.03	0.25	1.18	1.41	3.84	-0.278	16.59	0.137	5.49E-09	9.98E-05	0.12	0.07	12	0.229	31	0.194	0.032	0.426	0.347	0.255	0.202	0.229	0.268
Pu	LSI	L	12	0.79	3.40	1.48	0.26	2.55	0.20	1.51	1.34	4.91	-0.3	30.46	0.067	1.80E-07	5.53E-04	0.05	0.04	35	0.670	13	0.11	0.517	0.824	0.224	0.147	0.078	0.670	0.150
Py	LSI	L	5	0.29	2.46	0.51	0.27	2.59	0.20	1.49	1.34	4.56	-0.321	31.42	-0.031	2.09E-07	5.50E-04	0.00	0.00	49	0.849	3	0.023	0.847	0.851	0.053	0.044	0.003	0.849	0.033
Qu	LSI	L	12	0.79	3.34	0.95	0.26	2.46	0.20	1.46	1.34	4.69	-0.275	27.73	0.088	1.85E-07	5.56E-04	0.00	0.04	39	0.720	14	0.116	0.695	0.746	0.261	0.270	0.000	0.720	0.177
Ra	LSI	L	7	0.43	2.58	0.39	0.26	2.58	0.20	1.48	1.34	4.56	-0.319	31.32	0.040	2.15E-07	5.58E-04	0.00	0.00	51	0.867	6	0.065	0.886	0.849	0.177	0.054	0.000	0.867	0.077
Ri	LSI	L	10	0.64	3.08	0.67	0.26	2.47	0.20	1.48	1.34	4.48	-0.296	30.29	0.091	2.21E-07	5.70E-04	0.01	0.01	45	0.806	12	0.109	0.793	0.819	0.266	0.167	0.008	0.806	0.147
Ro	LSI	L	14	0.93	3.62	2.91	0.25	2.18	0.21	1.36	1.35	4.39	-0.225	22.97	0.234	1.39E-07	4.98E-04	0.19	0.18	19	0.320	44	0.307	0.032	0.609	0.517	0.515	0.312	0.320	0.448
Sl	LSI	L	13	0.86	3.49	1.47	0.25	2.40	0.20	1.44	1.33	4.42	-0.289	29.94	0.139	2.87E-07	6.51E-04	0.01	0.06	34	0.665	22	0.143	0.521	0.809	0.350	0.201	0.018	0.665	0.190
SyC	LSI	L	4	0.21	2.34	0.96	0.21	2.40	0.16	1.37	1.27	4.12	-0.32	36.60	-0.001	3.88E-06	2.34E-03	0.00	0.00	48	0.846	4	0.041	0.692	1.000	0.105	0.049	0.005	0.846	0.053
SyP	LSI	L	8	0.50	2.81	0.51	0.21	2.32	0.16	1.33	1.27	3.97	-0.31	34.47	0.050	4.22E-06	2.47E-03	0.07	0.07	52	0.893	11	0.102	0.847	0.939	0.194	0.098	0.107	0.893	0.133
Va	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.26	2.31	0.21	1.41	1.34	4.41	-0.269	24.42	0.112	1.54E-07	4.80E-04	0.08	0.09	20	0.325	28	0.165	0.000	0.650	0.303	0.299	0.126	0.325	0.243
Vi	LSI	L	9	0.57	2.99	0.68	0.26	2.47	0.20	1.48	1.35	4.59	-0.274	29.36	0.170	2.26E-07	5.69E-04	0.09	0.09	44	0.790	35	0.202	0.788	0.792	0.405	0.275	0.147	0.790	0.275
Vl	LSI	L	15	1.00	3.71	3.00	0.29	2.23	0.24	1.43	1.41	4.97	-0.234	18.48	0.113	1.30E-08	1.38E-04	0.00	0.01	13	0.240	25	0.152	0.000	0.480	0.305	0.471	0.000	0.240	0.258
Vz	LSI	L	9	0.57	2.95	0.67	0.26	2.38	0.20	1.37	1.34	4.23	-0.305	25.78	0.141	1.90E-07	5.44E-04	0.00	0.00	43	0.741	19	0.131	0.793	0.690	0.354	0.123	0.000	0.741	0.159
AiCS	SC	S	12	0.79	3.40	1.48	0.19	1.86	0.16	1.13	1.25	3.47	-0.199	21.68	0.143	8.43E-06	3.55E-03	0.51	0.16	29	0.544	48	0.399	0.517	0.572	0.357	0.642	0.835	0.544	0.611

Table S12: All genetic and genotypic indices computed on the 53 sampled populations. Each index was obtained from 15 individuals sampled in each population. (See spreadsheet supplementary material). *Mating* column indicates if the population was supposed to expressed a late-acting self-incompatible system (LSI) or be self-compatible (SC), the seven underlined populations being directly tested by controlled crosses using 15 plants randomly sampled in the population. *Morph* indicates the floral morph of the population. *G* is the number of multi-locus genotypes genotyped on the 15 sampled individuals per population; *R* is the genotypic diversity; *D** clonal heterogeneity; *Pareto's β* the clonal evenness; *HO*, the mean observed heterozygosity; *var(ho)*, the variance of the observed heterozygosity among loci; *HE*, the mean expected heterozygosity; *var(he)*, the variance of the expected heterozygosity among loci; *AE*, the mean effective number of alleles among loci; *var(Ae)*, the variance of the effective number of alleles among loci; *FIS*, the mean inbreeding coefficient; *var(FIS)*, the variance of the inbreeding coefficient among loci; *rd*, the population index of multilocus linkage disequilibrium; *PIDu* and *PIDSib*, unbiased probability of identity under panmixia and between sibs respectively; *Sg*, the estimate of selfing and *SE(Sg)* the standard error of estimate of selfing. Then, the relative rankings of populations according to different indices and the relative rankings of reproduction modes (see Material and Methods). Full table is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12760022>, tabulation “*Genetic indices per pop*”.

Stoeckel S, Becheler R, Portillo-Lemus L, Harang M, Besnard A-L, Lassalle G, Causse-Védrines R, Michon-Coudouel S, Park DJ, Pope BJ, Petit EJ, Barloy D (2024) Reproductive modes in populations of late-acting self-incompatible and self-compatible polyploid *Ludwigia grandiflora* subsp. *hexapetala* in western Europe. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.03.21.586104>

Population with missing genotype	nb_missing_genotypes	nb_individuals_concerned
Bléré_Ls	1	1
Chambéon_écopôle_du_Forez	2	2
Le_Port_Ls	1	1
Plougonver_Léguer	1	1
Quevillon	1	1
Rennes_apigné_prairie	1	1
Roost-Warendin	1	1
Saint_Aignan_Couflons_Ls	1	1
Vichy	1	1

Over single SNP genotypes	N	%age
single SNP genotype P(cad)>70%	28610	0.99965
single SNP genotype P(cad)≤70%	10	0.00035
total	28620	1

Over individuals	N	%age
nb_individuals_with_full_genotype	785	0.98742
nb_individuals_with_one_missing_genotype	10	0.01258
total	795	1

Table S13: Summary of the allele dosage. First subtable lists populations with individual genotyped with at least one individual with missing genotype at one locus. Second subtable reports the frequency of single SNP genotypes with posterior probability of allele dosage strictly superior to 70%. Third subtable reports the frequency of individuals with their 36 SNP genotypes assigned with posterior probability superior to 70%.

	G	H _O	H _E	A _E	R	β	F _{IS}	VarF _{IS}	r _d	PID _{SIB}	S _g	Σ _{clon}	Σ _{self}
G	-	0.438	0.013	0.009	***	***	***	***	0.057	0.008	0.008	***	***
H _O	0.076	-	***	***	0.397	0.462	0.122	0.025	0.653	***	0.032	0.065	0.142
H _E	0.244	0.742	-	***	0.01	0.014	0.212	***	0.026	***	0.844	***	0.372
A _E	0.255	0.722	0.82	-	0.008	0.013	0.353	***	0.094	***	0.347	***	0.845
R	0.991	0.083	0.251	0.258	-	***	***	***	0.052	0.007	0.005	***	***
β	0.91	0.071	0.238	0.24	0.919	-	***	***	0.126	0.009	0.004	***	***
F _{IS}	0.602	-0.144	0.116	0.086	0.603	0.557	-	***	***	0.163	***	***	***
VarF _{IS}	-0.579	-0.209	-0.435	-0.346	-0.589	-0.551	-0.626	-	***	***	***	***	***
r _d	0.187	0.042	0.207	0.156	0.19	0.148	0.432	-0.365	-	0.021	***	0.006	***
PID _{SIB}	0.259	0.729	0.981	0.833	0.265	0.251	0.13	-0.443	0.214	-	0.936	***	0.286
S _g	0.264	-0.202	-0.019	-0.089	0.277	0.28	0.542	-0.379	0.353	-0.008	-	***	***
Σ _{clon}	-0.79	-0.171	-0.376	-0.347	-0.799	-0.809	-0.604	0.756	-0.254	-0.387	-0.34	-	***
Σ _{self}	0.388	-0.136	0.083	0.018	0.399	0.361	0.723	-0.524	0.631	0.099	0.69	-0.451	-

Table S14: Correlations between genetic indices using non-parametric Kendall partial rank-order correlation. Below the diagonal, the values of the coefficient of correlation τ are consigned. Above, the related p-values are provided. Values inferior to the threshold 0.05, and the related coefficient τ were bold. The parameters Σ_{CLON} and Σ_{SELF} correspond to the sum of normalized indices sensitive to clonality and selfing, respectively.

Figure S12: Photos of somatic metaphase chromosomes indicating that L- and S-morph individuals that succeed to mate and to give full fruit set and 100% viable first- and second-generation descendants (Portillo-Lemus et al., 2021) also present the same number of chromosomes ($2n=10X=80$), belonging to the same taxon *Ludwigia grandiflora* subsp. *hexapetala*. We still didn't find *Ludwigia grandiflora* subsp. *grandiflora* karyotype in France ($2n=6X=48$, see Dandelot 2005, Barloy et al., 2024). **A:** somatic metaphase chromosomes from L-morph ($2n=10X=80$); **B:** somatic metaphase chromosomes from S-morph ($2n=10X=80$).

Figure S13: Akaike's information criterion (AIC) as function of the ploidy level on the likelihoods of the sequenced allele countings over all individuals. Tetraploidy, a ploidy 4x, presents the lowest AIC, and thus the best supported model to explain distribution of sequenced allele countings over all individuals, which confirm our initial SNP development to be sure of their ploidy level.

Figure S14.A: Correlation circles of the principal component analysis on the 17 centered and scaled genetic indices measured in 53 *Lgh* populations in western Europe. The first horizontal dimension accounting for 47.7% of the variance regroups indices related to clonality (number of genotypes *G*, genotypic diversity *R*, clonal heterogeneity *D*, clonal evenness *Beta_Pareto*, variance of Fis *varFis*, variance of expected heterozygosity *varHe*, variance of observed heterozygosity *varHo* and variance of effective number of alleles *varAe* between loci). The second vertical dimension accounting for 22.9% of the variance with a main contribution of estimate of selfing *Sg*. Other indices, *i.e.*, mean observed heterozygosity *Ho*, mean expected heterozygosity *He*, effective number of alleles *Ae*, inbreeding coefficient *Mfis*, linkage disequilibrium *rd*, standard error of estimate of selfing *SE.Sg*, unbiased probability of identity under panmixia *PIDu* and between sibs *PIDsib*. In blue and dashed lines, the predictions of Σ_{clon} (*Sclon*) and Σ_{self} (*Sself*) provided as supplementary variables.

Figure SI4.B: Bar plot of the genetic index contributions to the first principal component. The expected average contribution $1/(\text{number of genetic indices})$ is plotted as the red dashed line. VarFis and indices of genotypic diversity (Pareto, R, G & D) are the main contributors to the first component.

Figure SI4.C: Bar plot of the genetic index contributions to the second principal component. The expected average contribution $1/(\text{number of genetic indices})$ is plotted as the red dashed line. Estimates of selfing (Sg), mean observed heterozygosity (Ho), mean effective number of alleles (AE) and probabilities of identities (pid_u and pid_{sib}) are the main contributors to the second component.

Figure S14.D: Plot of the projection of each population onto the two first principal components. SC populations are plotted as red triangles and LSI populations as black diamonds. Concentration ellipses around LSI and SC populations are plotted in black and red, respectively. Barycenters of the two groups are represented as bigger black diamond and red triangle, respectively.

Figure S15: Relationship and correlation between Σ_{CLON} and genetic indices (R, Pareto β , MFis, VarFis, Ho, Ae, Sg, pidsib and \bar{r}_d). Per graph, all the 53 populations were plotted as black dots. *: $p < 0.05$, **: $p < 0.01$, ***: $p < 0.001$.

Figure S16: Relationship and correlation between Σ_{SELF} and genetic indices (R, Pareto β , MFis, VarFis, Ho, Ae, Sg, pidsib and \bar{r}_d). Per graph, all the 53 populations were plotted as black dots. *: p<0.05, **: p<0.01, ***: p<0.001.

Figure S17: Distributions of the logarithms of the number of ramets per genet in LSI (grey) and SC (white) populations. We report the Kruskal-Wallis probability that the two distributions are identical.